

STUDYING THE IMPACT OF BUS STOPS ON CITY ROADS AND STREETS ON TRAFFIC FLOW AND TRAFFIC SAFETY

Djuraev Akhmadjon Eshboyevich

Internal affairs department of Samarkand region

Road Safety Department officer lieutenant colonel

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ANNOTATION: This article presents the characteristics of the movement of minibuses according to the types of urban transport. In order to solve the problems that have a negative impact on the movement of city passenger transport, the preferential movement of vehicles on the central streets of Jizzakh was analyzed.

Key words: road network, bus, minibus, road traffic accident, driver, pedestrian, environment, car, road, collision, Operator, accident.

Nowadays, the number of cars in major cities of the world is increasing day by day. Such a situation can be seen in the Republic of Uzbekistan. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to increase the potential of the country's economy, the development of the automobile industry was launched. Automobilation has a positive effect on the economic growth of the society, but it also causes a number of negative consequences. As a result of the negative consequences of automobileization, many traffic accidents occur. This leads to the death or injury of a number of people, as well as a lot of material damage caused by traffic accidents, high level of noise in the region of city streets, roads passing through populated areas, etc. Blocking of streets by parked cars and finally, first of all, has a negative effect on the movement of city passenger transport [4]. For example, if we take the city of Jizzakh, the lack of special lanes for public transport moving in the mixed traffic flow or preferential movement at the traffic light object prevents them from working at the same time. As a result, the traffic speeds of passenger vehicles will decrease along with traffic jams.

It is known that the increase in the level of carization of the country, along with the strengthening of its economic and defense power, can lead to many negative consequences. Such negative consequences include an increase in the amount of traffic on highways, the density of traffic flow and the level of loading of roads due to the increase in the number of cars, the deterioration of the comfort for the driver to move on the roads, and ultimately the number of road traffic accidents (THA), in which people die. leads to an increase in the number of people falling and suffering various bodily injuries, a decrease in the speed of movement and many other similar negative consequences (noise, concentration

of exhaust gases in the air). According to the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, more than 55 million accidents occur in the world every year, in which more than 1.4 million people die, and more than 10 million people suffer various degrees of physical injuries. It can be seen from these that the increase in the level of automobileization leads to the complication of the problem of traffic safety, especially to higher requirements for the training of drivers. The work process of the driver is similar to the work of the manager (operator) of all other complex systems. It is related to the fact that the driver, like the operator, performs any operation (behavior), receives information, understands it and controls the result of his actions. At the same time, the driver's activity in driving a car differs from other operators in some ways. The operator can predict the state of the controlled system based on the monitoring devices, and his actions consist of maintaining the state or indicators of the object at a certain level. The driver does not have such opportunities. For example, if the car goes out of the lane to the right or left while moving in a straight line, the following driver will turn the steering wheel and return the car to its previous position, if the safety distance is reduced, reduce the speed and make the necessary provides a safety margin of l, etc. If the operator monitors the status of only one machine (system), the driver needs to monitor the actions of other traffic participants to ensure traffic safety. The driver may not receive such information in time, or as a result of insufficient information, he may behave incorrectly, which, in turn, may lead to traffic accidents.

The analysis of the conducted studies shows that road fogging works Babkov V.F., Abdurakhmanov R.A., Azizov S.Z. and other studies. In the mountainous region of the Republic of Uzbekistan, roads are divided by height above sea level. The main criterion for fogging is the traffic safety index of cars. In the studies, the factors influencing the traffic conditions were not systematically approached and analyzed, the theoretical foundations of the traffic conditions were improved, and the criteria for evaluating the traffic conditions were not included. [2, 3]

RESULTS

There are a number of issues that need to be resolved regarding the development of preferential movement of city passenger transport and the improvement of the quality of transport services provided to the population. These are: - Today, the competitiveness of city passenger vehicles compared to private vehicles has decreased a little. The reason for this is the higher speed of private vehicles than public vehicles, passengers. they choose it due to the superiority of their qualities, such as convenience, regularity of transportation,

and the favorable price of transportation for passengers. In addition to these, during peak hours of the day, delays of public transport vehicles, especially buses, increase in delay time, as a result of which the speed of movement decreases, as a result of disruptions in the regularity of traffic, the loss of time due to the waiting of passengers leads to the above reasons. All this has a negative effect on the economic indicators of public transport: - despite the presence of appropriate road markings and road marking lines on the roads, the city center with heavy traffic The first part of the carriageway is mainly used by public transport, and the entrances and exits of buses have become temporary accommodation for vehicles. - The main traffic-operational indicators of the routes passing through certain streets in Jizzakh city describe traffic (volume of traffic, structure of traffic, speed of traffic flow, density of traffic flow, traffic congestion), determine safety and road Indicators determining the condition of the road (road capacity, smoothness of the pavement, stability and gearing) are not maintained at the required level or are in need of maintenance at all.

This, in turn, has a negative impact on the movement of public transport; - artificial lighting is not fully provided on some streets where the routes travel. This causes a number of inconveniences to drivers during the dark and causes traffic accidents. In order to solve the problems mentioned above, which have a negative effect on the movement of city passenger transport, it is necessary to study the preferential movement of vehicles on the central streets of Jizzakh. The Department of Road Safety of the Jizzakh City Internal Affairs Department (IIB YHHB), Jizzakh Region, in order to solve the problems that have a negative impact on the safe movement of vehicles, ensure the safe movement of vehicles and prevent road traffic accidents It will be appropriate and will find its solution if it is solved by developing measures together with the transport department and all interested organizations [5, 12].

A. Navoi street in our city is considered one of the busiest streets, the total width of the road is 22 meters. The carriageway for cars and public transport is considered to be 3-lane, and the width of the lane in the direction is 3.5 meters. stations are built relatively close to the intersection and are slightly elevated from the ground for safety reasons. The general traffic section is separated by lanes. Sh.Rashidov street is one of the streets of Jizzakh city where cars and public transport move. The total width of the street is 22 meters and it is divided into 3 lanes. The width of each piece is 3.5 meters. According to the directions, the traffic sections are set at 10.5 meters. Independence Street is one of the central streets of our city. Car traffic is very heavy on this street. The total width of the street is 22 meters. The width of the carriageway is 11 meters and divided

into 3 lanes. The width of the lane is 3.5 meters. It is considered that passenger transportation will not be difficult in a place with low population density. In Kuala Lumpur, the capital of Malaysia (population 900,000), 400 minibuses have been put into operation, replacing 250-300 regular buses. Passengers are transported by minibuses for 8.2 km. Minibuses are cheaper than taxis. In a number of countries (USA, Germany, etc.), transport has reached the level of politics. For example, in the USA, transport corridors are built, roads to big cities are opened, and these roads are supported by the federal government. Large parking lots and information centers about buses have been built on the side of the corridors [2]. The system of collecting and transporting passengers can also be useful in our country, where the rate of automobileization is increasing.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the condition and condition of city passenger transport on the main streets of Jizzakh was determined and based on a comprehensive analysis, which was based on literature sources and internet information on foreign research. In the main streets of the city with public transport, the amount of traffic changes in the amount of 2500-3000 vehicles per hour in the morning "rush hours" at 800-1000 hours and in the evening at 1700-1800 hours by 2520-3050 vehicles per hour, and the traffic composition is 94-97 % passenger cars, 0.4-1.0 % trucks, 1.2 - 4%. bus, minibuses, and 0.2-0.6% were found.

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